

SEMAGLUTIDE REDUCED CARDIOVASCULAR EVENTS BY 20% IN CERTAIN ADULTS

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The purpose of the work: The purpose and significance of semaglutide effect on the cardiovascular outcome in order to investigate if the semaglutide 2.4 mg, long-acting GLP-1 RA, is more effective than a placebo in reducing cardiovascular event in the individuals having established cardiovascular disease who are also obese and do not yet have type II diabetes. Adherence to lifestyle guidelines aimed at reducing cardiovascular risk is provided for both semaglutide and placebo (Mares, Chatterjee, & Mukherjee, 2022).

Material and methods of research: In a double-blind manner, patients were randomized (1:1) for receiving either a placebo or once-daily oral semaglutide i.e. target dose of 14 mg. The stratification of the randomization process was based on presence of cardiovascular risks alone, evidence of chronic renal disease, or established cardiovascular illness.

Results of the study: Oral semaglutide or placebo was given to 3182 subjects. The patients' average age was 66, and 2695 (84.6%) had chronic renal disease or cardiovascular disease and were 50 or older. 15.9 months was the study median. 60 oral semaglutide patients (3.7%) and 75 placebo patients (4.9%) can have significant adverse cardiovascular events (hazard ratio, 0.79; 95% CI). By the end of the study, 82.1 percent of oral semaglutide-treated patients (1106 out of 1347) were taking 14 mg (Zhong et al., 2022).

Nonfatal myocardial infarction, 38 of 1590 patients (2.4%) and 30 of 1590 (2.0%), respectively (hazard ratio, 1.19; 95% CI); nonfatal stroke, 11 of 1592 (0.9%) and 15 of 1590 (1.2%) The oral semaglutide group had 25 deaths (1.5%) whereas the placebo group had 40 deaths (2.9%). More oral semaglutide users stopped due to gastrointestinal side effects (Husain et al., 2020).

Conclusions: Semaglutide, a newly licenced GLP-1RA, may promote weight loss because to its better glycemic efficiency. It is well recognised that semaglutide is cardiovascular-safe, like other GLP-1RAs. Future or present research includes subcutaneous semaglutide for obesity, oral semaglutide for cardiovascular disease and Type II Diabetes, and a weekly head-to-head trial. Novel cardiovascular treatments must be evaluated to guide clinical practice as the area grows. Semaglutide evaluations reveal its safety, efficacy, and cardiovascular effects.